

A proposed Image Processing Framework for Diagnosis of Anemia with Providing Proper Nutrition

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Abstract— Anemia is one of the most widespread diseases which people face in developing countries. The traditional method used to detect anemia is a blood sample test, but this method is costly and requires a lot of time. This paper aims to design an automatic, fast, and reliable system for detecting anemia for adults whether a man or a woman. Also, it aims to form daily healthy meals for adults after calculating their daily nutritional requirements using the food exchange system. The image processing techniques are used in the proposed system for analysis of the anterior conjunctiva of the eye, tongue, and nails. Features are extracted by many methods such as color coherence vector and local binary pattern. For classification process weighted Euclidean distance and k-nearest neighbor methods are used. Nutritional requirements are computed according to weight, height, age, and physical activity. Also, the proposed system offers a set of nutritional advice for healthy adults. The proposed system achieved a high performance level when compared with the results of laboratory analysis.

Keywords:- Anemia; Image Processing; Food Exchange System; Color Coherence Vector; Local Binary Pattern; Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix.

I. INTRODUCTION

A healthy balanced diet should contain a sufficient amount of iron to meet the needs of a person's body. Taking small amounts of iron, folic acid, and nutrients that boost iron absorption are the main factors for the high prevalence of anemia [1]. The level of blood Hemoglobin (Hb) is used for measuring anemia. Hb is a red blood cell protein that carries oxygen to all of the body cells [2]. The World Health Organization (WHO) statistics refer to people nearly 1.62 billion all over the world suffer from anemia. Anemia has the highest prevalence in countries in which income is low and middle [3]. The WHO organization defines anemia as Hb < 13 g/dL in adult men, <12 g/dL in non-pregnant adult women, and <11 g/dL in pregnant adult women [4]. Anemia has a bad effect on health, such as lethargy, difficulty in concentrating, and fatigue, which reduces economic productivity and life quality [5]. There are some methods to check for anemia or not. One of them is through a medical examination in a laboratory and others through consultation of a doctor [6]. For the rapid detection of anemia, the doctor examines the colors of the anterior conjunctiva of the eye, tongue, and fingernails. In the absence of anemia, the color of the anterior conjunctiva of the eye is full or almost complete redness. However, in the case of anemia, it is pale [7]. A healthy tongue should be pink and

covered with small nodules (papillae). Changes in color and texture of the tongue are signs of anemia [8]. In the absence of anemia, the nails color is pink. However, in the case of anemia, it is white or pale [9]. The main problem to detect anemia in some developing countries is the cost, which makes the people ignored to go to a laboratory or a doctor. Therefore, there is a need for other inexpensive, fast and accurate methods for detection of anemia.

Computer-aided diagnosis tool uses image processing techniques to help in increasing the diagnosis accuracy and also its speed [10]. So image processing in the field of medicine assists medical practitioners in diagnosing patient's disease [11].

There are few systems have developed for detection of anemia. K-means algorithm had proposed for detection of anemia based on the eye analysis by Sevani et al. [12]. Automated detection of anemia by analyzing the anterior conjunctiva pallor of the eye through a non-invasive visual method had designed by Tamir et al. [13]. Nail image processing for different disease diagnoses had presented by Indi et al. [14]. Nail color changes had used using the support vector machine to diagnose the disease by Nithya et al. [15]. C4.5 algorithms had used for analyzing human hand nail to identify many diseases by Gunge et al. [16]. An automated tongue diagnostic system on mobile-enabled platforms had proposed by Tania et al. [17]. The pallor sites of conjunctiva and tongue had analyzed by classifiers called Azure-based Generalized flow for Medical Image Classification (AGMIC) for anemia screening by Roychowdhury et al. [18].

From the above mentioned, it is clear that the detection of anemia can base on the analysis of anterior conjunctiva pallor of the eye, tongue, and nails. Therefore, this paper aims to design an automated, quick, simple, reliable, and inexpensive system for the detection of anemia in adults by using the image processing technique. And also, it aims to form daily healthy meals from Egyptian food items, especially those who suffered from anemia according to their daily nutritional requirements.

II. THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The proposed system consists of two stages. The first stage, is the diagnosis, and the second stage, is the nutrition. In the diagnosis stage, the anterior conjunctiva pallor of the eye, tongue, and nails are analyzed to know whether anemia or not.

In the nutrition stage sex, age, weight, height, physical activity, pregnancy stage (in case of pregnancy), and age of the baby (in case of lactating) are entered for presenting suitable nutrient meals for anemia patients. Fig. 1 shows the proposed framework for anemia detection.

Fig. 1. The proposed framework for anemia detection

A. Diagnosis Stage

The diagnosis stage aims to decide that the adult suffers from anemia or not from his eye, tongue, and fingernails images. Fig. 2 shows the anterior conjunctiva of eye, tongue, and fingernail images in case of no- anemia and anemia.

Fig. 2. The anterior conjunctiva of eye, tongue, and fingernail images in case of: (a) no- anemia and (b) anemia

These images are analysed using image processing techniques as follows:

1) Acquisition of the Images

The images of anterior conjunctiva of the eye, mouth, and fingers are taken using two types of cameras, a digital camera (Panasonic DMC-LX5), and the internal smartphone camera (Samsung m30). Fig. 3 shows examples of an eye, a tongue, and a fingernail images.

Fig. 3. Examples of an eye, a tongue, and a fingernail images

2) Images Pre-processing

Image pre-processing is a significant step to enhance the image quality. The image pre-processing step is explained as follows:

- Resizing images of the eye and mouth using "imresize" Matlab function and the size is 256 × 256 pixels.
- Enhancing images by applying Histogram Equalization (HE) using "histeq" function in Matlab as shown in fig. 4.

Fig. 4. The eye, the tongue and, the fingernail images after applying (HE)

3) Image Segmentation

Segmentation of the eye image is performed as follows:

- Extraction of the red channel only from image, as shown in fig. (5-a).
- Creating a binary mask, as shown in fig. (5-b), using a fixed threshold value of "225", which was reached after many tests and experiments on trial and error basis. The red channel values of the eye image are compared to the threshold value. If a value was higher than the threshold value, the respective pixel position value is given 1 in a new matrix, otherwise 0. The new matrix contains only black and white pixels. The pixel value of 0 is a black area of conjunctiva pallor, and the pixel value 1 identifies a white area.
- Applying the median filter method using "medfilt2" function in Matlab for clearing image, as shown in fig. (5-c).
- Removing background, as shown in fig. (5-d), using function "imclearborder" in Matlab. It removes the frame without any object from the frame with the object.
- Extraction of the largest area (the conjunctiva area of the eye) using 'bwareafilt' Matlab function, as shown in fig. (5-e).

Fig. 5 (a-e). Eye image segmentation processes

Segmentation of the mouth image is as follows:

- Converting mouth image into HSV using function "rgb2hsv" in Matlab, as shown in fig. (6-a). HSV is used to distinguish a specific color object. It represents pixels as Hue (H defines the color), Saturation (S specifies color purity), and Value (V defines the brightness) [19-21].
- Getting Hue value, as shown in fig. (6-b), which provides a suitable gray image that can be used to classify objects based on the color content.
- Applying thresholding using "graythresh" function in Matlab [22] which calculates the global image threshold from a gray image using the "Otsu" method. The global threshold T is used with "imbinarize" to convert a gray image to a binary image. Fig. (6-c) shows creating binary mask.
- Applying opening-by-reconstruction and closing-by-reconstruction morphological operations to remove destruction that occurs after applying thresholding [23]. Opening-by-reconstruction is an erosion followed by reconstruction. Erosion clears structures that are smaller in size than of the structuring element [24]. It is done using "imerode" and "imreconstruct" Matlab functions as shown in fig. (6-d). Closing-by-reconstruction is a dilation followed by a reconstruction. Dilation process makes an object grow by size [25]. It is done using functions "imdilate" and "imreconstruct" as shown in fig. (6-e).
- Applying median filter using "medfilt2" function in Matlab, as shown in fig. (6-f).
- Extracting the largest region (tongue area) using "bwareafilt" function as shown in fig. (6-g).

Fig. 6 (a-g). Mouth image segmentation processes

Segmentation of the finger image is as follows:

- Converting finger image into HSV as shown in fig. (7-a).
- Getting Hue value as shown in fig. (7-b).

- Creating binary mask using "graythresh" function as shown in fig. (7-c).
- Applying median filter to clear finger image as shown in fig. (7-d).
- Filling image using "imfill" function in Matlab as shown in fig. (7-e). The morphological filling is one of the simplest methods to fill holes. A hole is a set of background pixels that cannot be reached by filling in the background from the edge of the image [26].
- Extracting of the largest area (fingernail area) as shown in fig. (7-f) using "bwareafilt" function.

Fig. 7 (a-f). Finger image segmentation processes

4) Feature Extraction

There are many methods that are used in the proposed system for feature extraction. These methods are Color Coherence Vector (CCV), color moments, Local Binary Pattern (LBP) and Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM). These methods can be described as follows.

- Color Coherence Vector

For a given discredited color, some of the pixels will be coherent, and others will be incoherent. The number of coherent pixels of the j th discrete color is named α_j , and the number of incoherent pixels is called β_j . The total number of pixels with that color is $\alpha_j + \beta_j$, and so a color histogram would summarize an image as [27-28]:

$$\langle \alpha_1 + \beta_1, \dots, \alpha_n + \beta_n \rangle \quad (1)$$

Image color coherence pair's vector contains:

$$\langle (\alpha_1 + \beta_1), \dots, (\alpha_n + \beta_n) \rangle \quad (2)$$

Due to the relationship of the red and the white colors with the color of eye conjunctiva, tongue and fingernail, eight features have been selected from CCV. These features are (red- red blue- red green- white) coherent and (red- red blue- red green- white) incoherent.

- Color Moments

The mean (μ), the variance (v), the standard deviation (σ), the skewness (S) and the kurtosis (K) moments are extracted for each of the three color channels (R, G, B) of tongue and fingernail images, using the following equations [29-31]:

$$\mu_i = \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{1}{N} p_{ij} \quad (3)$$

$$v_i = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (p_{ij} - \mu_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_i = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (p_{ij} - \mu_i)^2} \quad (5)$$

$$S_i = \sqrt[3]{\left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (p_{ij} - \mu_i)^3\right)} \quad (6)$$

$$K_i = \sqrt[4]{\left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N (p_{ij} - \mu_i)^4\right)} \quad (7)$$

Where:

N: Number of pixels in the image.

p_{ij} : Value of the j^{th} pixel of the image at the i^{th} color channel.

Accordingly, one can get fifteen features for each tongue or nail image using color moments.

- Local Binary Pattern

Each pixel in tongue image is compared with its eight neighbours. Then, the information is encoded in an 8-bit integer value. This encoding can be considered as a transformation of the input image into the LBP image [32-33]. The histogram of the LBP image is used for tongue texture feature extraction as shown in figures (8-9).

Fig. 8. LBP operator

Fig. 9. Tongue image, LBP coded image, and its accompanied histogram

- Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix

GLCM is used to extract fingernail texture features. These features are calculated using the following formulas [34-35]:

$$Energy = \sum_{i,j} p(i, j)^2 \quad (8)$$

Where:

i, j : are a single pixel.

$p(i, j)$: is the probability that two pixels with a specified separation have grey levels i and j .

$$Contrast = \sum_{i,j} |i - j|^2 p(i, j) \quad (9)$$

$$Correlation = \sum_{i,j} \frac{(i - \mu_i)(j - \mu_j) p(i, j)}{\sigma_i \sigma_j} \quad (10)$$

Where:

μ_i and μ_j : represent the horizontal and the vertical means in the matrix.

σ_i and σ_j : represent standard deviation.

$$Homogeneity = \sum_{i,j} \frac{p(i, j)}{1 + |i - j|} \quad (11)$$

Table 1 shows the type and the number of extracted features from eye conjunctiva, tongue and fingernail images.

TABLE1

THE TYPE AND THE NUMBER OF EXTRACTED FEATURES FROM EYE CONJUNCTIVA, TONGUE AND NAIL IMAGES

Features	CCV	Moments	LBP	GLCM	Total
Eye	8	---	---	---	8
Tongue	8	15	1	---	24
Fingernail	8	15	---	4	27

5) Image Classification

There are two methods that are used in the proposed system for classification. These methods are Weighted Euclidean Distance (WED) and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN). The detailed analysis of these methods is as follows.

- Weighted Euclidean Distance

WED measure is used for matching the conjunctiva pallor of the eye and tongue. The formula of WED is as follows [36]:

$$d(v, v^k) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n p_i (v_i - v_i^k)^2} \quad (12)$$

Where:

v_i : to balance the variations in the dynamic range.

P_i : the weight added to the component.

k : is the matched image index.

$$P_i = \frac{N}{\sum_{k=1}^N (v_i^k - \bar{v}_i)^2} \quad (13)$$

N = the number of images in databases.

$$\bar{v}_i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N v_i^k}{N} \quad (14)$$

- K-Nearest Neighbor

KNN is classified based on the majority of the K-nearest neighbour category. The distance between the query sample and all training samples are computed. Then, it is sorted, and

the closest neighbours are determined based on the minimum distance K^{th} . The category Y of the nearest neighbours is collected. The majority category of the nearest neighbours is used to predict the value of the query sample. The Euclidean is the most widely used distance function with k-NN [37-38].

$$d(x,y) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - y_i)^2} \tag{15}$$

Where:

x : features vector of dimension n for the query sample.
 y : features vector of dimension n for training samples.

Figures (10), (12) and (14) show flowcharts to feature extraction and saving for all databases template images of eye conjunctiva, tongue, and fingernail. Figures (11), (13) and (15) show flowcharts for classification.

Fig. 10. Flow chart for eye conjunctiva feature extraction and saving for all databases template images

Fig. 11. Flow chart for eye conjunctiva classification

Fig. 12. Flow chart for tongue feature extraction and saving for all database template images

Fig. 13. Flow chart for tongue classification

Fig. 15. Flow chart for fingernail classification

Fig. 14. Flow chart for fingernail feature extraction and saving for all databases template images

6) Final Decision

After analysing the conjunctiva of the eye, tongue and nails, there will be three decisions obtained from them with the presence of anemia or not. Depending on the principle that anemia symptoms such as (pallor of the conjunctiva of the eye - white tongue and white nails) can show one, some or all of them. So, if any of the three decisions is the presence of anemia, the final decision is the presence of anemia.

B. Nutrition Stage

The nutrition stage is presented to provide suitable nutrition for patients who suffered from anemia. Also, it is interested in providing nutritional advice for healthy adults. The details analysis of this stage is explained as follows:

1) Input Personal Data

Persons who deal with the proposed system are adult (men, pregnant women, non-pregnant women and lactating women). The users are registered their personal data through the user interface which specially designed for this purpose as shown in table 2.

TABLE 2

DESCRIPTION OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM INPUTS

Input	Description
Age	(Years)
Sex	- Male - Female
Height	(cm)
Current Weight	(Kg)
Woman Status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pregnant Non-pregnant. Lactating woman.
Pregnancy Stage (In case of Pregnancy)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1st Trimester Pregnancy (1-3) months 2nd Trimester Pregnancy (4-6) months 3rd Trimester Pregnancy (7-9) months
Weight before pregnancy (In case of Pregnancy)	(Kg)
Age of the Baby (In case of lactation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (0-6) Months (7-12) Months
Physical Activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sedentary - Light Active - Active - Very Active

2) Calculate Body Mass Index

Body mass index (BMI) is a ratio used to determine healthy weight ranges for humans. BMI is calculated as follows [39-40]:

$$BMI (Kg/m^2) = \frac{Weight (Kg)}{Height^2 (m^2)} \quad (16)$$

The WHO determined the body mass index for underweight, normal weight, and obesity [41] as the following table:

TABLE 3

THE BODY MASS INDEX FOR UNDERWEIGHT, NORMAL WEIGHT AND OBESITY

Weight	BMI Value
Underweight (thin)	BMI < 18.5 Kg/m ²
Normal weight	BMI of 18.5–24.9 kg/m ²
Obesity	BMI ≥ 25 kg/m ²

3) Calculate Total Energy

Estimated Energy Requirements for adults (EER) can be calculated with the following equations [42]:

- Calculate EER for a man

- **EER for normal man** = 662– (9.53*Age) +PA*[(15.91 *weight) + (539.6 * height)]
- **EER for an underweight man** = EER for normal man+500
- **EER for an obese man** = 1086– (10.1*Age) +PA*[(13.7*weight) + (416* height)] -500

- Calculate EER for a non- pregnant woman

- **EER for normal and non-pregnant woman**= 354 – (6.91*Age) +PA* [(9.36*weight) + (726 * height)]
- **EER for an underweight, non-pregnant woman** = EER for normal and non-pregnant woman +500
- **EER for an obese non-pregnant woman** = 448 – (7.95 *Age) +PA*[(11.4 *weight) + (619 * height)] -500

- Calculate EER for a Pregnant Woman

- **EER for a normal or underweight, pregnant woman** = 354 – (6.91*Age) +PA* [(9.36*weight) + (726 * height)]
- **EER for a normal or underweight, pregnant woman in 1st trimester** = EER for a normal or underweight, pregnant + 0
- **EER for a normal or underweight, pregnant woman in 2nd trimester** = EER for a normal or underweight, pregnant + 340
- **EER for a normal or underweight, pregnant woman in 3rd trimester** = EER for a normal or underweight, pregnant + 452

- Calculate EER for a Lactating Woman

- **EER for a normal lactating woman who her baby age is from 0 to 6 months** = 354 – (6.91*Age) +PA* [(9.36 *weight) + (726 * height)] +328
- **EER for normal lactating woman who her baby age is from 7 to 12 months** = 354 – (6.91*Age) +PA* [(9.36 *weight) + (726 * height)] +400
- **EER for an underweight lactating woman** = EER for normal lactating woman +500
- **EER for an obese lactating woman who her baby age is from 0 to 6 months**= 448 – (7.95 *Age) +PA*[(11.4 *weight) + (619 * height)] +328
- **EER for an obese lactating woman who her baby age is from 7 to 12 months**=448 – (7.95 *Age) +PA*[(11.4 *weight) + (619 * height)] +400

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Where:

Age: in years, Height: in meters, Weight: referred to the current weight in kilograms, PA: The physical activity coefficient as shown in table 4 [43]

TABLE 4

THE PHYSICAL ACTIVITY COEFFICIENT FOR A MAN AND A WOMAN

PA for	Sedentary	Low Active	Active	Very Active
Man				
Normal	1.0	1.11	1.25	1.48
Obese	1.0	1.12	1.29	1.59
woman				
Normal	1.0	1.12	1.27	1.45
Obese	1.0	1.16	1.27	1.44

4) Calculate Requirements of Nutrients

The calculated energy (EER) is distributed into the main macronutrients, carbohydrates, proteins, and fats. Table 5 shows the calculation of adult's nutrients requirements [44-50].

TABLE 5

CALCULATION OF NUTRIENTS REQUIREMENTS FOR ADULTS

Nutrition Needs	
Protein	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protein calories for man and non-pregnant woman = 10% (EER) Protein calories for a pregnant woman = 10% (EER) + 30 Protein calories for a lactating woman = 10% (EER) + 20 $Protein\ grams = Calculated\ protein\ calories / 4$
Fats	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fats calories = 25% (EER) $Fats\ grams = Calculated\ fats\ calories / 9$
Sugar Added	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Added sugar calories = 8% (EER) $Added\ sugar\ grams = Calculated\ fats\ calories / 4$
Carbohydrates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carbohydrates calories = EER - [Protein calories+ Fats calories+ Added Sugar calories] $Carbohydrates\ grams = Carbohydrates\ calories / 4$

5) Calculate Food Exchange Groups Per Day

A committee of the American Diabetes Association designed the food exchange system [51]. The food exchange system divided into six groups. Each food group contains a list of weighed or measured foods which have almost the same nutritional value. Table 6 shows the food exchange groups [52-59].

6) Distribution of Food Exchange groups Per Meals

A database had built for the distribution of food exchange groups per meal. The daily meals for adults consist of five meals, namely; Breakfast (B), Lunch (L), Supper (S), Mid-morning snack (Sn₁), and Mid-afternoon snack (Sn₂). Table 7 shows an example of the distribution of food exchange groups per meal for an underweight man who suffered from anemia.

7) Detection of the Desired Food Items in the Daily Meals

A list of Egyptian food items from each food exchange group appears in each meal. Then, the adult chooses his desired food from them.

8) Displaying the Final Meals

At the end, the selected food items in each meal, which is desired by the Egyptian adult, will display as his daily meals.

TABLE 6

FOOD EXCHANGE GROUPS

Food Group	CHO grams	Protein grams	Fat grams	Energy KCal
Starch/Bread	15	2	--	70
Meat	--	7	3	55
Med. Fat	---	7	5.5	77.5
High Fat	---	7	8	100
Vegetables	5	2	--	25
Fruits	10	--	--	40
Milk				
Skim Milk	12	8	----	80 kcal
Low fat Milk	12	8	5	120
Whole Milk	12	8	8	150
Fat	---	---	5	45

TABLE 7

EXAMPLE OF DISTRIBUTION OF FOOD EXCHANGE GROUPS PER DAILY MEALS FOR AN UNDERWEIGHT MAN WHO SUFFERED FROM ANEMIA

Food Group	Food Exchanges Units	B	L	S	Sn ₁	Sn ₂
Milk	2	1	0	1	0	0
Meat	6	1	2	1	1	1
Vegetables	5	1	3	1	0	0
Added Sugar	6	2	0	2	1	1
Bread	15	4	4	4	2	1
Fruits	11	2	2	2	2	3
Fats	10	2	2	2	2	2

III. Application and Experimental Results

A. Description of the proposed application

The proposed system for the detection and nutrition of anemia patients is designed using Matlab language (R2018b). The proposed system Graphical User Interface (GUI) is shown in fig. 16. A button of "Anemia Detection from Eye" is pressed to enter to a new window that detect anemia from eye and give decision and so on for the tongue and nails. After entering the eye, tongue, and nails windows, press a button "Final Decision" to get the final decision of the three decisions together. If the final decision is "anemia", a button called " Nutrition Stage" is appeared to go to the nutrition stage. Otherwise, a button called "General advice for anemia" is appeared to give advice for healthy adults. Figures from 17 to 19 show eye, tongue and nail windows.

Fig. 16. The proposed system Graphical User Interface

Fig. 18. Tongue window for detection of anemia

Fig. 17. Eye window for detection of anemia

Fig. 19. Fingernails window for detection of anemia

Fig. 20 shows that the final decision for the three decisions from eye, tongue and nails is "Anemia". So, the button "Nutrition Stage" is appeared for going to the second step for anemia nutrition, as shown in fig. 21.

Fig. 20. The final decision for the three decisions from eye, tongue and nails

Fig. 21. Anemia nutrition stage

B. Evaluation of the proposed System

The database used is consisted of 400 images, 100 images for each adult category whether (men- pregnant women - non-pregnant women - lactating women). Three metrics are used for evaluation purposes. Precision (P) calculates the ration of relevant images retrieved to the total number of images retrieved (relevant and non-relevant images). Recall (R) calculates the ratio of no. of relevant images retrieved to the total number of relevant images in Database. F-Measure (F-Score) calculates by compute the mean of precision and recall. These metrics equations are as follows [60]:

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}} \quad (17)$$

$$R = \frac{(TP)}{(Tp) + (FN)} = \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Negative}} \quad (18)$$

$$F - \text{Score} = 2 \times \frac{2(P \times R)}{(P + R)} = 2 \times \frac{(\text{Precision} \times \text{Recall})}{(\text{Precision} + \text{Recall})} \quad (19)$$

Figures 22 -24 show precision, recall and f-measure curves for anemia images retrieval.

Fig. 22. Precision curve

Fig. 23. Recall curve

Fig. 24. F-measure curve

IV. Conclusion

Anemia is a condition in which the total level of haemoglobin or the number of red blood cells is severely low. Nutrient deficiency is one of the most common causes of anemia. Therefore, this paper presents a novel anemia diagnosis and nutrition system for adults. Diagnosis is based on analysis colors of the anterior conjunctiva of the eye, tongue, and nails. Besides, it introduces daily healthy meals from Egyptian food items using the food exchange system after calculating the daily nutritional requirements for an adult. The performance of the proposed system has reached to 95%. The importance of the system comes from it provides an automated, quick, inexpensive, easy to use, and reliable method for detection of anemia. Also, it can be used anytime and anywhere. In addition, this system helps in increasing public awareness to improve human health. Moreover, the ability to detect anemia in its early stage.

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